

Studies on the kinetics of complex formation in the tetrachloropalladate(II) – ligand systems : Ligands being thiosemicarbazide, amidinothiourea and biguanide

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Abstract : Based on detailed kinetic studies on these systems, plausible reaction schemes have been proposed that account for the experimental observations; component rate constants of the derived rate-laws have been evaluated by graphical/least square procedure. The results indicated the reactivity order thiosemicarbazide > amidinothiourea >> biguanide. The results of the amidinothiourea system afford a meaningful comparison with the corresponding results for the tetrachloroplatinate(II) reported by us previously (see text); k_{Pd}/k_{Pt} is of the order of 10^4 . Comparison of the ΔS^\ddagger values for the two systems suggests that in both the cases the reaction proceeds by an interchange process with bond formation being significant in case of Pt(II) while bond dissociation is significant in case of Pd(II).

Thiosemicarbazide (tsc, $H_2NC(S)NHNH_2$)¹, amidinothiourea (guanylthiourea, amtu, $H_2NC(NH)C(S)NH_2$)² and biguanide (big, $H_2NC(NH)NHC(NH)NH_2$)³ are bidentate ligands; the first two are (S,N) donors, while big is (N,N) donor utilising the N of the two C(NH) units⁴ rather than C(NH) and NH_2 believed earlier⁵.

In an earlier communication⁶ we reported the results of kinetic studies on the tetrachloroplatinate(II) – amidinothiourea system⁶. Results of similar studies on the tetrachloropalladate(II) – ligand systems (ligand = tsc, amtu, big) are reported in this communication.

Results and discussion

Spectral observations in the $PdCl_4^{2-}$ – amtu system in presence of excess Cl^- ion and H^+ ion indicated complex formation (see Fig. 1); the composition of the complex formed was found to be 1 : 1 by the mole ratio method⁷, viz., $PdCl_2(L)$ (L = amtu). Similar results were obtained for L = tsc. In case of L = big, similar observations (see Fig. 2) indicated formation of the $PdCl_2(big)$, which was isolated previously⁸, followed by a much slower formation of the known⁹ $Pd(big)_2^{2+}$.

From the previously reported⁶ pK_a value (ca. 5.6) of $amtuH^+$ it follows that in the range of acid concentrations (0.05–0.25 M) used in the kinetic studies the amtu

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra in aqueous solution : (A) K_2PdCl_4 , 0.0005 M in 1 M KCl solution, (B) and (C) K_2PdCl_4 , 0.0005 M + amidinothiourea 0.01 M in (HCl + KCl) 1 M [HCl, 0.1 M in (B) and 0.2 M in (C)]. No change in the spectrum observed on increasing the concentration of amidinothiourea to 0.05 M or decreasing to 0.005 M.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra in aqueous solution : (A) K_2PdCl_4 , 0.0005 M in 1 M KCl solution, (B) K_2PdCl_4 , 0.0005 M + biguanide dihydrochloride, big.2HCl, 0.005 M + HCl 0.005 M + KCl 0.985 M, after keeping for 30 min at room temperature, C to H are the spectra of the solution (B) recorded after 1 h, 2 h, 3 h, 4 h, 5 h and 24 h respectively. (B) corresponds to that of $PdCl_2(big)$ and (H) corresponds to that of $Pd(big)_2^{2+}$ (see text, Refs. 8 and 9).

(0.005–0.025 M) will be present virtually exclusively in the protonated form and hence the non-dependence of the observed pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , on concentration of H^+ ion suggests that the reacting ligand is $amuH^+$.

Thiosemicarbazide is also moderately basic¹⁰ and the non-dependence of the k_{obs} on H^+ concentration in this case also suggests that in the experimental solutions the tsc exists virtually exclusively as $tscH^+$ (hence its pK_a must be ≥ 2.5 , which is not unlikely as the corresponding value for thiourea¹¹ is 2.03 (at 25 °C) and tsc is expected to be a stronger base), and $tscH^+$ is the reacting species. The following general scheme is proposed for the reactions with tsc and amtu which accounts for the experimentally observed facts (L = tsc, amtu) :

Concentration of the species II as evaluated on the basis of steady state principle is,

$$[II] = k_1 [I] / (k_2 [LH^+] + k_{-1} [Cl^-])$$

Hence, from the rate expression,

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 [II] [LH^+] + k_3 [I] [LH^+]$$

the following expression is obtained for the pseudo-first order rate constant :

$$k_{obs} = (k_1 k_2 [LH^+]) / (k_{-1} [Cl^-] + k_2 [LH^+] + k_3 [LH^+]) \quad (1)$$

where $[LH^+] = T_L$

Two limiting situations are possible :

(a) If $k_2 [LH^+] \gg [k_{-1} [Cl^-]]$, then eq. (1) transforms into,

$$k_{obs} = k_1 + k_3 [LH^+] \quad (2)$$

Hence, plot of k_{obs} vs T_L is linear (see Fig. 3).

The k_1 and k_3 values (see Table 5) were evaluated by the method of least square. The k_1 values thus obtained are in fair agreement with the values reported¹² from studies on the aquation of $PdCl_4^{2-}$ as shown in Table 1.

Table 1			
Temp. °C	25	35	Ref.
$k_1, s^{-1} (\mu, 1 M) :$	9.5	23.5	This work
	8.9	21.0	12

This agreement further lends credence to the proposed reaction scheme. The k_3 values are quoted in Table 5.

(b) If $k_{-1} [Cl^-] \gg k_2 [LH^+]$ then the eq. (1) transforms into,

$$k_{obs} = (K_1 k_2 / [Cl^-] + k_3) [LH^+] \quad (3)$$

In eq. (3) $K_1 = k_1 / k_{-1}$ is the equilibrium constant for the

Fig. 5. Formation of $PdCl_2(amtu)$ from $PdCl_4^{2-}$ and amidinothiourea in aqueous acid – chloride (HCl + KCl) media : $T_L = [LH^+]$; $[PdCl_4^{2-}]$, 0.0005 M; $[H^+]$, 0.05 M; μ , 1 M (HCl+ KCl + KNO_3); Temp. 30 °C.

Based on this scheme the rate of the reaction is to be expressed as,

$$\text{Rate} = k_b [III] + k_3 [I] [LH^+] \quad (4)$$

Hence, we need to evaluate the values of the concentrations [III] and $[LH^+]$ to arrive at the rate expression in the proper form.

For [III] we need to have knowledge of the equilibrium constants K_1 and K_a ; the K_a values were evaluated under the experimental conditions by the usual pH method as in the case of the analogous complex of Pt(II) reported by us earlier⁶. The graphical evaluation procedure used for this evaluation also yielded the values of K_1 (Table 2). These were in agreement with literature values (*loc. cit.*). The values evaluated for K_a are given in Table 3.

Table 3			
Temp. °C	25	30	35
$10^8 K_a$, M (μ , 1 M, KCl)	9.3	7.4	6.1
ΔH , kJ mol ⁻¹	-33.3 ± 2.6		
ΔS , J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	-245 ± 8		

Following the usual physico-chemical principles the concentration of the species III of the above scheme is,

$$[III] = K_1 K_a [I] / [H^+] [Cl^-] \quad (5)$$

The ligand biguanide is known to be a strong base that can add up to $2H^+$ for which the reported $\log K_H$ values at 32 °C (I, 0.05 M) are 11.5 and 2.93 respectively¹⁴. Hence, in the range of acid concentrations (0.003–0.013 M) used in our experiments the biguanide ($big.2HCl$, 0.005–0.015 M) will be mostly present as $bigH_2^{2+}$ in equilibrium with $bigH^+$:

Hence, to evaluate the concentration of $bigH^+$ in the solution we need to know the K_H values under the experimental conditions. These were evaluated using the usual pH method following the procedure as reported earlier for amidinothiourea⁶. The values thus obtained are reported in Table 4.

Table 4			
Temp. °C	30	35	40
$10^2 K_H$, M ⁻¹ (μ , 1 M, KCl)	10.2	9.6	8.7

Considering the equilibrium as in eq. (6) the concentration of LH^+ (L = biguanide, big) is,

$$[\text{LH}^+] = T_L / (1 + K_H [\text{H}^+]) \quad (7)$$

where $T_L = [\text{LH}^+] + [\text{LH}_2^{2+}]$

Substituting the values of [III] and $[\text{LH}^+]$ from eqs. (5) and (7) in eq. (4) we obtain,

$$\text{Rate} = \{ (k_b K_1 K_a / [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]) + (k_3 T_L / (1 + K_H [\text{H}^+])) \} [\text{I}] \quad (8)$$

Under pseudo-first order conditions, this leads to,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_b K_1 K_a / [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-] + k_3 T_L / (1 + K_H [\text{H}^+]) \quad (9)$$

If the $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ are held constant then eq. (9) transforms into the following well known expression observed in general for ligand replacement reactions of square-planar complexes :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_L T_L \quad (10)$$

Hence at fixed concentrations of H^+ and Cl^- the plot of k_{obs} vs T_L is linear with k_0 as intercept and k_L as slope. For such plots at a fixed $[\text{H}^+]$ and different $[\text{Cl}^-]$ the slope is the same but intercept decreases with increasing $[\text{Cl}^-]$ (see Fig. 6). For similar plots at fixed $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and different $[\text{H}^+]$ both intercept (I) and slope (S) decrease with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ (see Fig. 7). The value of k_b was evaluated from the linear plot of I vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 8), with prior knowledge of the K_1 and K_a values (*loc. cit.*). The k_3 (and also of K_H) were evaluated from the linear plot of $1/S$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 9). The K_H values thus obtained were in agreement with the corresponding values determined directly (*loc. cit.*).

In all the reactions in the schemes mentioned above, the LH^+ binds as a unidentate ligand followed by much faster ring closure forming the product complex $\text{PdCl}_2\text{-(L)}$ in which the L is bonded bidentately.

A comparison of the k_3 values for these ligands with those of a few other ligands given in Table 6 is interesting. In cases of both thiosemicarbazide and amidinothiourea the k_3 values are of the order of $10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and hence comparable to the corresponding value for thiourea which binds through the S of the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ unit to the "soft" Pd(II) centre. This suggests that the unidentate binding of these two ligands in the rate determining step involves Pd-S bond formation. But, for the corresponding reaction of NH_3 (N donor) the k_3 value is very much smaller (see Table 6). Biguanide being an N,N donor also reacts significantly slower by a factor of 10^4 . Based on the k_3

Table 5. Rate constants for the $\text{PdCl}_4^{2-} - \text{L}$ systems (μ , 1 M)

(A) L = Thiosemicarbazide :		
Temp. °C	k_1, s^{-1}	$10^{-3} k_3, \text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
25	9.5 ± 0.03	2.6 ± 0.01
30	15.5 ± 0.05	3.4 ± 0.03
35	23.5 ± 0.08	3.9 ± 0.03
40	33.1 ± 0.08	4.7 ± 0.05
$\Delta H^\ddagger, \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	61.9 ± 1.6	27.4 ± 1.7
$\Delta S^\ddagger, \text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	-19.7 ± 6.2	-88.4 ± 5.2
(B) L = Amidinothiourea :		
Temp. °C		$10^{-3} k_3, \text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
25		1.7 ± 0.01
30		2.3 ± 0.01
35		3.0 ± 0.02
40		3.8 ± 0.02
$\Delta H^\ddagger, \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$		38.7 ± 0.7
$\Delta S^\ddagger, \text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$		-54.1 ± 2.3
(C) L = Biguanide		
Temp. °C	$10^{-2} k_b, \text{s}^{-1}$	$10^2 k_3, \text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
25	4.6 ± 0.02	41 ± 0.3
30	8.6 ± 0.05	62.9 ± 0.2
35	16.9 ± 0.1	88.3 ± 0.5
40	28.9 ± 0.2	131.2 ± 1.0
$\Delta H^\ddagger, \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	93.9 ± 3.9	57.8 ± 1.5
$\Delta S^\ddagger, \text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	120.1 ± 8.5	-59.9 ± 2.5

Fig. 6. Formation of $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{big})$ from PdCl_4^{2-} and biguanide, L, in aqueous acid - chloride media : Effect of T_L on k_{obs} at different $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and fixed $[\text{H}^+]$ [PdCl_4^{2-} , 0.0005 M; $[\text{H}^+]$, 0.003 M; $[\text{Cl}^-]$, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0 M for A, B and C respectively; μ , 1 M ($\text{HCl} + \text{KCl} + \text{KNO}_3$); Temp. 30 °C.

Fig. 7. Formation of $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{big})$ from PdCl_4^{2-} and biguanide, L in aqueous acid - chloride media : Effect of T_L on k_{obs} at different $[\text{H}^+]$ and fixed $[\text{Cl}^-]$: $[\text{PdCl}_4^{2-}]$, 0.0005 M; $[\text{H}^+]$, 0.003, 0.005, 0.006, 0.008 and 0.013 M for A, B, C, D and E respectively; $[\text{Cl}^-]$, 1 M; μ , 1 M; Temp. 30 °C.

Fig. 8. Evaluation of k_b for PdCl_4^{2-} - biguanide system (see text) : $[\text{Cl}^-]$, 1 M; μ , 1 M; Temp. 30, 35 and 40 °C for A, B and C respectively.

values the reactivity order for L is thiosemicarbazide > amidinothiourea >> biguanide and the ΔH^\ddagger values increase in the reverse order.

Fig. 9. Evaluation of k_3 and K_H for the PdCl_4^{2-} - biguanide system (see text) : $[\text{Cl}^-]$, 1 M; μ , 1 M; Temp. 30, 35 and 40 °C for A, B and C respectively.

The general mechanistic feature of ligand replacement reactions of Pt(II) complexes is best regarded as an interchange process with both bond formation and bond rupture having contributions in generating the transition state¹⁹. In the case of a reaction between a substrate bearing a charge of 2- with the attacking nucleophile bearing a charge of 1+ there will be partial charge neutralisation on bond formation leading to desolvation making a positive contribution to the entropy change, while dissociation of the M-Cl bond will cause a negative contribution to the entropy change due to solvation of the free Cl^- ion. The fairly high negative values of ΔS^\ddagger for the k_3 path observed for the reactions of the Pd(II) complex reported in this communication are in accord with a process in which there is significant bond dissociation in the transition state and much less significant bond formation (hence I_d process); but for the reaction of the analogous Pt(II) complex with amidinothiourea the corresponding value for the k_3 path is significantly positive ($96.2 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)⁶ suggesting bond formation being more significant than bond dissociation in this case (hence I_a process).

The rate constant for the aquation of $\text{PdCl}_3(\text{OH}_2)^-$ to

Table 6. Comparison of the kinetic parameters for reaction of PdCl_4^{2-} with different ligands at 25 °C

Ligand	$k_3, \text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	$\Delta H^\ddagger, \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta S^\ddagger, \text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	Ref.
NH_3	33	–	–	15
enH^+	296	–	–	16
Thiourea	9.1×10^3	25.1	–81.6	17
Selenourea	4.5×10^4	18.4	–109.8	17
$\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2)_2$	4.9×10^{-3}	83.7	+58.6	18
$\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{CH}_2\text{NHMe})_2$	5.5×10^{-4}	96.3	+83.7	18
Thiosemicarbazide ^a	2.6×10^3	27.4	–88.4	This work
Amidinothiourea ^a	1.7×10^3	38.7	–54.1	This work
Biguanide ^a	0.41	57.8	–59.9	This work

^aFor the reactions of corresponding LH^+ (see text).

cis- $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{OH})_2$ is 9.1 s^{-1} at 25 °C (see Ref. 13(b)), while that of $\text{PdCl}_3(\text{OH})^{2-}$ is 460 s^{-1} (see k_b in Table 5(C)). Such greater reactivity of hydroxo complexes is a general phenomenon and many such cases are well documented in literature²⁰. Thus, for anation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{OH})^{3-}$ with SCN^- the rate constant at 25 °C is $1.3 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ but the corresponding value for $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{OH})^{2-}$ is 1.9×10^{-2} (Ref. 21). Comparison of the k_3 values of reactions of MCl_4^{2-} ($\text{M} = \text{Pt}$ (Ref. 6), Pd (present communication)) shows that for $\text{L} = \text{amidinothiourea}$, at 35 °C the $k_{\text{Pd}}/k_{\text{Pt}} = 3 \times 10^3/0.14 = 2.1 \times 10^4$ which is also an usual behaviour²⁰. For the aquation reactions of MCl_4^{2-} ($\text{M} = \text{Pd}, \text{Pt}$) the rate constant values at 25 °C are 9.5 s^{-1} (see Table 1) and $3.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Ref. 22(a), $4.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ reported by Martin (Jr.) *et al.*^{22(b)}) for $\text{Pd}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{II})$ species respectively yielding $k_{\text{Pd}}/k_{\text{Pt}} = 2.5 \times 10^5$. For several systems $k_{\text{Pd}}/k_{\text{Pt}} \sim 10^3\text{--}10^5$ (Ref. 20). The k_b path observed for the reaction of biguanide is not seen in the cases of thiosemicarbazide and amidinothiourea because in these cases the initial aqua complex is transformed into the product in a much faster process than in the case of far less reactive biguanide, as seen from the k_3 values; in their cases the aqua species does not survive long enough to permit the reaction involving the hydroxo species. This k_b path has also been observed in the reaction of the analogous complex of $\text{Pt}(\text{II})$ ⁶ with amidinothiourea, as in this system the reaction is very much slower than for $\text{Pd}(\text{II})$.

Experimental

Chemically pure grade (GR, E. Merck, Germany) thiosemicarbazide was used. Amidinothiourea was pre-

pared in pure state by known method²³ and its purity was checked by elemental (N and S) analysis and by its melting point (170 °C). Biguanide sulfate, bigH_2SO_4 , was prepared in pure state following known method²⁴ and its purity was checked by chemical analysis (N and SO_4^{2-}). From this the corresponding bigH_2Cl_2 was prepared in solution by treatment with requisite amount of BaCl_2 and filtering off the precipitated BaSO_4 . Stock solution of K_2PdCl_4 was prepared by dissolving pure PdCl_2 (Arora Mathey, India) in aqueous KCl solution and was standardised by the usual gravimetric procedure as $\text{Pd}(\text{dmg})_2$ ($\text{dmgH} = \text{dimethylglyoxime}$)²⁵. This solution was kept in Jena (Germany) glass bottle protected from light. All other chemicals used were of analytically pure grade and the solutions were prepared in double distilled water (see Ref. 6).

The instruments used and the experimental procedures were the same as reported earlier⁶. The reactions with thiosemicarbazide and amidinothiourea were followed by stopped-flow spectrophotometry at 470 nm, while that with biguanide was followed by conventional spectrophotometry, at 470 nm, by carrying out the reaction in the spectrometer cell kept in a specially designed jacketed cell holder, which was kept at the desired temperature (± 0.2 °C) by rapidly circulating thermostated water, and measuring the absorbance at intervals of 1–2 min.

Note : The authors would like to point out that molar concentrations expressed by M are, as per modern convention, mol dm^{-3} ; for simplicity M has been used as per earlier convention. Similarly, the unit $\text{M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ used for rate constant, as per modern convention, is $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

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